

Research on SPOC teaching mode of international students in high vocational schools in post MOOC era

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Abstract

With the rapid growth of the number of foreign students in China, and the education of foreign students in China is changing from “elite” education to “popular” education. It is imperative to innovate the Chinese teaching mode for foreign students in China. By building the “CAPACP” teaching mode, constructing the curriculum system of ‘one body and two wings’, setting up the evaluation system for foreign students, this paper completes the overall design of the curriculum under the SPOC teaching mode, builds a structured curriculum resource database, realizes the integration of language application ability and cross-cultural communication ability for foreign students, promotes the internationalization of the college, promotes the spread of internationalization of Chinese culture.

Keywords: SPOC teaching mode. CAPACP teaching mode. Curriculum system of one body and two wings. Evaluation system. Overall design of the curriculum. Structured curriculum resource database.

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Introduction

With the continuous improvement of China's comprehensive national strength and international influence, and with the continuous improvement of China's higher education opening to the outside world, the number of foreign students in China is increasing year by year. Since the "Belt and Road" initiative, the number of foreign students along the Silk Road is increasing rapidly. However, due to China's late start of teaching Chinese as a foreign language (TCFL), the lack of teachers and the lag of educational methods restrict the development of the International students' work in colleges and universities. Therefore, it is more and more important to strengthen the teaching level for TCFL.

At present, although there are many modes of TCFL, most of them belong to the traditional subject-based teaching mode, and there is little research on the reform of teaching mode and curriculum construction based on information technology and Internet application.

Through the innovation experiment of the small private online course (SPOC) teaching mode in the post massive open online course (MOOC) era, this paper takes the information technology and the network as the platform, hoping to provide a new way of thinking for TCFL in higher vocational education.

Sketch of MOOC and SPOC teaching

Professor Armando Fox, MOOC director at the University of California, Berkeley, introduced a small restricted online course (Small Private Online Course) in 2013, in response to MOOC problems and criticism and questioning SPOC limit the size of students to dozens to hundreds of people, and set the admission conditions for the learners of the course, it is a more refined course type. The basic teaching process of the SPOC is: the teacher uses the MOOC resources of the relevant courses to obtain the high quality teaching video, and arranges these video materials to the students as pre-class homework, the students self-study after class, then the teacher communicates, interacts and answers questions with the students in the physical classroom, answers students' questions face to face and handles homework, masters the effect of self-study before class and the comprehensible level of the key knowledge, then adjusts the teaching content and teaching progress in time, and finally do the evaluation. Compared with MOOC, the SPOC improves the completion rate of the course, the platform and mechanisms are relatively simple, guided by the effectiveness of learning, and the teaching resources are relatively concentrated.

The SPOC teaching mode for higher vocational colleges under the post MOOC era

1. Construct the "CAPACP" teaching model under the SPOC teaching mode

The process for "CAPACP" teaching model is: curriculum resources-autonomous learning-problem inquiry-classroom activities-evaluation feedback-ability enhancement.

It is a circular promoting teaching mode. The model has a clear and explicit definition of what teachers and students should do and how to do in the classroom.

"CAPACP" teaching model is mainly divided into before-class, in-class and after-class.

Figure 1. "CAPACP" Teaching Model

A. Pre-class period

The pre-class period includes teacher's preparation before class and students' pre-class study.

1. Teachers preparation before class

Teachers should make and upload teaching videos. Based on the analysis of students' study situation, the teacher make the teaching videos combined with synthetic consideration of the teaching material, the student and the grammar characteristic, and then uploads them to the public network platform. The video shows the grammatical structure, and the grammatical and semantic relations in the structure of the difficulty stratification, according to a certain order to do explanation. Teachers also set up making sentences based on the given picture, sentence patterns, imitation of sentences and other questions for students to self-test. In the public network platform, students download, watch grammar teaching video, and put forward their own questions, teachers choose to answer some typical questions or give collective guidance according to the students' raising questions. For students' individual questions, teachers can choose to answer them or ask other students to help answer them, while for students' common problems, teachers can collect and synthesize them and solve them uniformly in the classroom.

Taking Chinese Comprehensive as an example, teachers have prepared a large number of micro-class videos for students to download and watch in order to fully prepare and learn before class.

According to the characteristics of our college's zero-base adult students, "Chinese comprehensive" is divided into eight modules: greeting, introduction, inquiry, plan, diet, shopping, study and leisure, and travel.

2. Students' pre-class study

According to the teacher's request, the students should preview before class. The preview is not limited to the understanding of new words and texts, but also through watching grammar teaching video to understand its basic structure. The video can be downloaded and watched repeatedly. Students can learn independently and understand the grammatical structure, which greatly reduces the time of listening in class and improves the learning efficiency. The flexible teaching environment means that students can arrange their own learning progress before class. When problems are difficult to understand, they can not only be repeatedly examined according to the video, but also can be discussed online with teachers and students at any time. After watching the video, the students should complete the corresponding grammar questions. These questions mainly include making sentences based on given pictures, arranging words, imitating sentences and other more mechanical exercises.

Students can do self-check according to the answers to the test questions, determine which type of mistakes they make, ask questions, and other students or teachers could answer them on the network platform. These problems mainly involve grammatical and semantic aspects, not communicative pragmatic aspects.

In a word, the students have mastered the basic grammar knowledge in the pre-class stage, and the learning autonomy in the classroom will be stronger, and they can carry out communicative exercises more actively to achieve their own learning goals.

By making a large number of micro-class videos and PPTs, each section is also equipped with corresponding exercises for different difficulty levels, so that students can test their knowledge according to the test questions. At the same time, students need to do self-check, trying to find out their problems and doubts and then ask the teacher when having class at school.

B. Class period

1. Teachers' Summary of Difficulties

The teacher summarizes the problems raised by the students before class and the students' universal mistakes, explains the problems of the students in the grammar study, and emphasizes the contents that are prone to make mistakes, in order to arouse the students' attention. Through the preparation of relevant practice materials for classroom training, consolidate learning results.

2. Classroom Activities

After learning a grammar content, most students have a strong desire to use the grammar, but because of the limitations of the use environment and conditions, the students do not know the appropriate time to use. Students will have two kinds of situations, one is when to use but didn't use, another is use it when there is no need. Therefore, on the basis of students have mastered the grammatical structure, teachers can carry out communicative classroom activities, such as group discussion, role-playing, task completion and other diversified communicative activities.

3. Results Reporting

Foreign students cooperate to complete communicative classroom activities, and summarize classroom activities by making reports, communicative conversations, among others.

4. Feedback

Under the SPOC teaching mode, the foreign students study step by step, through the theoretical study of grammatical structure, carrying out communicative exercises, and then inputting the effective context through the perceptual knowledge, rising to the rational understanding of the deep understanding of grammar, and then form a habitual language expression. Through a large number of contextual exercises, students can truly internalize knowledge and skills, and also promote student-to student communication and teacher -to student communication.

C. After-school period

Effective Evaluation

In the SPOC teaching model, the teacher's evaluation is all-round, including the evaluation of pre-class preparation, classroom performance and after-class homework.

It includes whether students make full use of pre-class teaching video to study, whether students independently complete the test questions in the video, whether students participate in cooperative learning discussion, answering questions and other links, and whether students effectively carry out activities with others in the classroom.

After the completion of teaching activities, under the guidance of teachers students carry out mutual evaluation, fill out the mutual evaluation form the teacher well prepared. Such as evaluating your classmate's level of master of the learning content, participation rate, whether effectively answer other students' questions, the circumstances of cooperation with others in class.

2. Assignment

Through the communicative practice of in-class period, students have internalized grammar knowledge. In order to consolidate the knowledge, teachers can arrange summative assignments, such as summing up the contents of classroom communication training, writing summary reports, or writing a diary of the classroom practice process. The arrangement of these assignments is mainly combined with oral expression ability in classroom activities. Training students' written expression ability is a useful supplement to students' grammar learning and helps to consolidate their grammar knowledge.

2. Construct the curriculum system of "one body and two wings"

The curriculum design is one of the most important parts for teaching design, and it is the main way to realize the teaching goal and decompose the teaching content. According to the types and characteristics of different courses, this paper constructs a curriculum system based on comprehensive Chinese, with Chinese listening and Chinese speaking and Chinese culture as the wings.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration for "One Body, Two Wings" curriculum system and "Structured" curriculum content

The main feature of Comprehensive Chinese is comprehensive teaching. The main task of it is to carry out the language elements, pragmatic rules and cultural background knowledge, to train language skills and communicative skills, and to combine the language elements, pragmatic rules and related cultural background knowledge with language training skills and communicative skills.

The comprehensive course aims at cultivating students' grammar consciousness and systematically mastering grammar knowledge, which is the basis of various skills training such as listening, speaking, reading and writing. Therefore, in the curriculum system of "one body and two wings", "Chinese Comprehensive" accounts for 45% in the whole curriculum system.

Chinese Listening is a language skill class. Through the study of listening class, foreign students can master some Chinese listening comprehension skills and successfully complete the complex listening comprehension process. The listening class is closely related to Chinese Comprehensive.

Chinese Speaking is a special skill course, which trains foreign students' language skills and corresponding language communication skills.

The students learned Chinese pronunciation and basic words and basic grammar in the course of "Chinese Comprehensive", and in Chinese Speaking class, they developed the ability of using Chinese for oral communication in real life. As a skillful course, Chinese Listening and Chinese Speaking apply the language elements, grammar rules and related cultural background knowledge to practical communication skills, which account for 45% of the curriculum system.

The Chinese Culture includes the Chinese culture experience part and the Chinese culture elective courses. Teacher will take students to experience the culture out of class. Through cultural experience, foreign students not only exercise basic Chinese language skills and basic communicative competence, but also understand the connotation of Chinese culture. Chinese culture elective courses include calligraphy, table tennis, folk songs, paper-cut and other courses with Chinese cultural characteristics. Cultural experience and Chinese culture elective courses account for 10% in the curriculum system.

Table 1. Schedule of teaching processes in the 2020 talent training program

Course Module	Course code	Course Name	Credits	Class hours			First year	
				Total hours	Theory	Practice	Week 1	Week 2
Professional competence courses	32180	Chinese Experience	16	272	136	136	17	17
	32181	Chinese Listening	8	136	68	68	17	17
	32182	Chinese Speaking	8	136	68	68	17	17
	32240	Reading and Writing	8	136	68	68	17	17
	Subtotal (92 percent of total class hours)			40	680	340	340	
Career development courses	33279	Chinese Experience	2	24	0	24	3	3
		Chinese culture elective (calligraphy, folk songs)	1	16	8	8	8	
		Chinese culture elective (table tennis, paper-cut)	1	16	8	8		8
	Subtotal (8 percent of total class hours)			4	56	16	40	
Total			44	736	356	380		

Table 2. Comprehensive practice in the 2020 Talent Training Program

Serial	Name of Integrated Practical Teaching Course		Opening of semester	Number of weeks	Hours	Credits
1	Chinese Cultural Experience 1	Organization of Mid-Autumn Festival celebrations Learn about the history and culture of the Mid-Autumn Festival Visit Zhoucun Ancient Mall Knowledge of relevant cultural knowledge Organize students to study dumplings Understanding the customs and culture of the New Year	1	1	12	1
2	Chinese Cultural Experience 2	Zongzi Learn about Dragon Boat Experience tea culture and learn tea etiquette Visit the pottery department	2	1	12	1
Subtotal				2	24	2

Table 3. List of public elective courses in the 2020 talent training program

Course name	Course content	Opening of semester	Hours of study	Credits
Public elective courses	Chinese cultural module (4 parts) Calligraphy Folk songs Paper cutting Ping-pong	1-2	32	2

3. The overall design of CFLC under SPOC teaching mode

The teaching step design of SPOC teaching mode is the basis of ensuring each whole teaching process, and involves every link in teaching. According to the characteristics of SPOC teaching mode, the teaching steps include: the before-class preparation and the relative reservation tasks, the acquisition of students' before-class knowledge, and the consolidation of students' knowledge internalization in class.

A. Preparation

Early preparation includes four parts. First, teaching object analysis. There are 20 students from the primary level: thirteen (13) Kyrgyz students, three (3) Yemeni students, and four (4) Russian students. Their basic vocabulary is about 400 to 500, and they can complete simple daily Chinese communication and can be assisted by Pinyin for autonomous learning. All 20 students have a good foundation of English and can use English to explain vocabulary.

Secondly, analyze the teaching objectives. The requirement for students is to memorize new words before class and understand the structure and usage of language points. Thirdly, arrange the teaching resources. Besides teaching materials such as CD-ROM and dialogue recording, teachers should make teaching courseware for pre-class self-study which will be uploaded on platform.

Those teaching courseware is mainly PowerPoint presentation (PPT) and micro-class video. The presentation way is to record the courseware with pictures into video mode with audio. The video contains words learning (21 words), grammar learning (modal complement), example sentence display, grammar structure learning, text learning and so on.

B. Access to pre-class knowledge

Students are not limited to watch the courseware before class to study, students complete part of the study, and should sort out the incomprehensible content, then participate in online communication at a fixed time, asking teachers or seeking help from students. After the exchange, the students need to participate in the test, complete the electronic version of the test paper to test the effect of self-study. Finally, record the blind spots and confusion points and watch the video again or study in the next day's class.

Teachers analyze students' autonomous learning before class. Through the analysis of the problems in the students' online communication and the more problems in the test results, teachers can find out the origin of the problem, explain this part in detail in the following class, and prepare the relevant exercises.

C. In-class knowledge internalization

Before class, students have a deep understanding of new words and language points. At the beginning of class, questions and answers should be arranged to help students focus on the importance and deep understanding of the knowledge. Teachers need to make a summary after collecting questions, displaying on the PPT and student group discussion. Difficult problems cannot be directly thrown to students to solve, teachers should first simply explain. In addition, teachers set aside time for students to ask questions and answer individual questions, because this can make up for the teachers' missing questions before class because of their lack of understanding of the students' learning situation.

Show of learning results. This part uses the group text performance or retell, the text content quick answer, simulates the real scene dialogue and so on.

Personalized guidance for students. Teachers should solve problems for students step by step in every link in the class. After individual or group display, teachers should correct and demonstrate the students' words and sentences, and teachers should sum up the class.

4. Build a structured curriculum resource database for TCFL

Based on the principle of "practicability, sharing, persistence and foresight", the four-step curriculum framework of "curriculum overall design → teaching module → teaching unit → knowledge + ability + culture" is constructed, the "structured" curriculum is formed, which is systematic and split, the structured resource database is created. And the interactive curriculum platform is built which is visual, doable, measurable, articulable, accessible and extensible.

Figure 3. Diagram of a structured curriculum resource base

The construction of structured curriculum resource database provides a guarantee for foreign students to realize "individualized" Chinese learning. Foreign students can arrange their own time to study on the network teaching platform and master the initiative of learning. By using the online study before class, the foreign students carefully watch the micro-class explanation, PPT display, detailed explanation of teaching plan and pre-class exercises of each teaching module, so as to understand the key points of difficulties, improve the learning efficiency, solve the problem of insufficient classroom hours, provide conditions for students with learning difficulties, meet the requirements of individualized learning, and improve the interest of most students. Using the network platform to carry out the interaction and communication between teachers and students before, during and after class, teachers' evaluation of students and feedback of students' class situation can be realized through the network comprehensive teaching platform, which is helpful for teachers to fully master the circumstances of students' understanding of knowledge, as well as helpful for the teachers to adjust the content and progress of classroom teaching at any time, improving the efficiency of classroom teaching, and promote the improvement of teachers' overall quality.

The effectiveness of SPOC teaching model

From November 2017 to May 2019, a total of 98 students took Hanyu Shuiping Kaoshi (HSK) or Chinese level tests from Levels 3 to 6. Eleven of them signed up and passed the HSK level 3, 65 people passed HSK Level 4, nine passed the HSK Level 5, and only one person passed HSK Level 6. The total number for passing is 86, which accounts for 87.8% out of 98. In 2017, only two people took the test, and only one passed. Compared with 2017, we can see there is a qualitative leap in students' learning enthusiasm and HSK achievements.

Conclusion

Although through the exploration and perfection of the reform of the SPOC teaching mode, the overall teachers teaching ability has been improved, with the further development of the national "Belt and Road" strategy, more and more foreign students from various countries will come to Zibo Vocational Institute to study Chinese. We should continue to discuss how to carry out SPOC teaching for foreign students at different levels in the future work and research.

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